

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2
ISSUE 11

JANUARY-MARCH ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

MARIANO D. GILLO

Associate Professor

Eastern Visayas State University

Mariano.gillo@evsu.edu.ph

“HAIKU: PARUPARO AT BULAKLAK”

Pakpak makulay
Bulaklak mag-ingat ka
Lason ay dala

Bagong panahon
Paruparo’y iba na
Sakit ang dulot

Maging maingat
Bulaklak na maganda
Sa pagdapo n’ya

’wag padadala
Kanyang kulay na taglay
Nagiging itim

Paruparo ka
Bulaklak ay ingatan
At magmahalan